

Groups	Sample size
EBS Training Course for professionals and interested parties	38
Pregnant women and partners	38 pregnant women and three partners
School brigade	136
Photovoice	55
<i>Aedes</i> hunters	110
Community surveillance	60

Figure 1. Sample size of groups that participated in the intervention.